

Formation Constants of the Chelates of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-methylamine with some Bivalent Metal Ions

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Potentiometric studies have been carried on metal complexes of Cu^{+2} , Ni^{+2} , Co^{+2} , and Zn^{+2} with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-methylamine. The dissociation constants ($\text{p}K_1$ and $\text{p}K_2$) of the reagent and the formation constants of its metal complexes have been determined by Bjerrum's method at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at ionic strength 0.1M in 75:25 per cent (v/v) dioxan-water medium. The order of stability of chelates is found to be $\text{Cu} > \text{Ni} > \text{Co} > \text{Zn}$, which is in agreement with that of Maley and Mellor.

LITERATURE survey indicates that no systematic study of the stabilities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-methylamine and its metal chelates with bivalent metal ions appears to have been carried out.

In the present communication the successive stability constants of the complexes of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-methylamine with some bivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti.¹

Experimental

The Corning model 12, a precision research pH meter with a wide range glass electrode and a calomel reference electrode was used for the pH measurements. The meter has an arrangement for normal and expanded scale. The smallest scale division on the expanded scale is 0.005 pH unit.

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-methylamine was synthesised and repeatedly crystallised to get an analytically pure sample (m.p.² 132° - 133°).

All the chemicals used except the ligand and the perchloric acid were of B.D.H. analytical grade. The perchloric acid used was of E Merck G. R. grade.

The medium of titration was dioxan-water mixture containing 75 per cent (v/v) of dioxan. The dioxan used for the experiments was purified by the method described by Vogel.³ Distilled water, redistilled over alkaline potassium permanganate and made free from carbon dioxide by boiling, was used throughout the investigation. Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain a constant ionic strength (0.1M). The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling nitrogen gas through the solutions. All the metal perchlorate solutions were standardised complexometrically⁴ by E.D.T.A. titrations. All measurements were made at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (1.092M) solution, keeping the total volume 40 ml.

(i) 5 ml of (0.16M) HClO_4 + 5 ml of (0.64M) NaClO_4 + 30 ml of dioxan.

(ii) 5 ml of (0.16M) HClO_4 + 5 ml of (0.64M) NaClO_4 + requisite amount of the reagent accurately weighed to give 0.01M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml of dioxan.

(iii) 5 ml of (0.64M) NaClO_4 + 5 ml of (0.024M) metal salt solution in (0.16M) HClO_4 + requisite amount of the reagent accurately weighed to give 0.01M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml of dioxan.

The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti¹ was applied to find out the values of \bar{n} and pL.

Results and Discussion

From the titration curves using the solutions (i) and (ii), \bar{n}_A values at various 'B' values (pH meter readings) were calculated, and the curve between 'B' and the corresponding \bar{n}_A values was plotted (Fig. 1). The

Fig. 1.
2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-Methylamine Formation Curve.

formation curve extends over a range $0.71 < \bar{n}_A < 1.94$ and is wavelike. This indicates the formation of the species HL and H_2^+L , i. e. the protonated nitrogen and the phenolic hydrogen are completely dissociable in steps, separable. The value of pK_1^H only, could be evaluated from half integral point at $\bar{n}_A = 1.5$. The value of pK_1^H could not be found by half integral as well as graphical method. It was however determined by least square method.

Fig. 2
2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-Methylamine.

A plot of $\log \left[\frac{2 - \bar{n}_A}{1 - \bar{n}_A} \right]$ against 'B' was also drawn (Fig. 2). From this curve the value of practical pK_1^H was calculated. The two values agree quite well.

Fig. 3
Metal-Ligand Systems of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-Methylamine Formation Curves.

From the titration curves of solutions (ii) and (iii) \bar{n} and pL values were calculated. The \bar{n} values obtained are up to 1.0 and hence $\log K_1$ values only could be determined by half integral and graphical methods.

The \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of the metal complex-ion equilibria (Fig. 3). From these formation curves the values of stability constants, $\log K_1$ were computed which correspond to pL values at $\bar{n} = 0.5$.

Fig. 4
2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-Methylamine.

A plot of $\log \left[\frac{\bar{n}}{1 - \bar{n}} \right]$ against pL for the different metal systems was also drawn (Fig. 4). From these curves the values of $\log K_1$ were evaluated. The values obtained by both the methods agree quite well except in the case of Co^{+2} where the $\log K_1$ value had to be determined by graphical method on extrapolation of the curve.

The most representative values are recorded in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES (a)

t = 30°		μ = 0.1			
Cations	H ⁺	Cu ⁺²	Ni ⁺²	Co ⁺²	Zn ⁺²
log K ₁	10.46	13.80	8.75	7.85	7.65
log K ₂	8.80	—	—	—	—

(a) H⁺, K₁ and K₂ correspond to the species LH and LH₂ respectively while for metal ions K₁ and K₂ correspond to the species ML and ML₂ respectively.

The order of stability of bivalent metal chelates was $Cu^{+2} > Ni^{+2} > Co^{+2} > Zn^{+2}$. The order is in agreement with that of Maley and Mellor⁵.

Fig. 5
Formation Constants and Fundamental Properties of
2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene Methylamine-Complexes.

In similarity with the observations made by Calvin and Melchoir⁶ in the case of 5-salicylaldehyde-sulphonate, a correlation for the series of Co, Ni, Cu and

Zn with the second ionisation potential of the gaseous atoms was also observed by the authors in their study of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-methylamine. This is indicated graphically in Fig. 5, obtained by plotting the stability constants and the ionization potentials as a function of the atomic number.

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